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KEYS TO HAPPINESS: EXPLORING THE DETERMINANTS OF JOB SATISFACTION IN PRIVATE SCHOOLS OF AFGHANISTAN

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The main objective of this research is to analyze the determinants of job satisfaction among teachers in private schools in Afghanistan. This study utilizes the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ) as its foundational framework. The investigated factors include achievement, recognition, advancement, compensation, working conditions, job security, and coworker relationships. Furthermore, job satisfaction is considered a latent variable. Data were gathered through a thoroughly structured and randomly distributed

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questionnaire, which included demographic information (age, gender, education, and work experience) as well as inquiries related to the research variables. The sample consisted of 206 respondents drawn from the target population. The collected data are tested for reliability and consistency before further analysis. Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was employed to assess the data and derive conclusions. The findings reveal that all the examined factors significantly contribute to job satisfaction in the studied private schools. The current study has theoretical implications due to the fact that the findings are achieved through accepted scientific research methods. In addition to that, it has practical implications as well, because the managers in educational institutions and other related stakeholders can make informed decisions based on the findings of this study.

Keywords: Job Advancement, Working Condition, High School, Job Security

1. Introduction

There are various definitions available in the literature of organizational research. American psychologist Locke (1969) defines job satisfaction as “the pleasurable emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job as achieving or facilitating the achievement of one's job values” (p. 316). Job satisfaction encompasses a mental, behavioral, and job-related response from employees regarding their sense of fulfillment at work. It reflects the attitudes and behaviors employees exhibit toward various aspects of their job, such as compensation, authority, and peer relationships, which can be linked to specific outcomes (Ashraf, Ahmad, Shaikh, Bhatti, & Soomro, 2013)¹.

Job satisfaction is consistently identified as one of the most extensively studied topics within the field of industrial and organizational psychology (Dormann & Zapf, 2001). The importance of this topic can primarily be attributed to two major considerations: First, the investigation of job satisfaction is critical for all stakeholders interested in evaluating and improving working conditions, including elements such as task variety, responsibility, and communication requirements (Hackman & Oldham, 1980, as cited in Dormann & Zapf, 2001). Second, job satisfaction is frequently analyzed in relation to various outcome variables, such

¹ Given the Statement by the Executive Committee of the German Research Foundation (DFG) we would like to state, that we used Chat GPT for the following purposes: Improvement of sentence structure, spelling and search for synonyms.

as absenteeism (Breugh, 1981); (Keller, 1983); (Tharenou, 1993), fluctuation (Farkas & Tetrick, 1989); (Rusbult & Farrel, 1983), organizational inefficiency (Gottfredson & Holland, 1990), and sabotage (Chen & Spector, 1992). This is largely due to the widespread perception that job satisfaction serves as a primary causal factor for these issues.

Therefore, in recognition of the significance of this topic, the current study is undertaken. Similar to many other research domains in Afghanistan, empirical studies on employee satisfaction are notably insufficient. To identify evidence-based factors contributing to job satisfaction within educational institutions, it is essential to conduct comprehensive empirical research on this topic in Afghanistan. This study aims to address this gap by examining the determinants of job satisfaction among teachers in private schools in Kabul. The findings of this research will provide valuable insights for educational organizations, enabling them to implement strategies that effectively enhance employee satisfaction and, consequently, improve overall organizational performance.

The target population for this study comprises teachers employed in private schools in Kabul, Afghanistan. For sampling, we employed probability sampling, specifically opting for a random sampling technique. The sample included 224 teachers from various private schools in Kabul. Private schools in Afghanistan operate as independent, profit-driven educational institutions funded through private investments. These schools are characterized by unique attributes such as talented teachers, superior academic programs, and conducive learning environments. Consequently, private schools significantly contribute to the educational landscape of Afghanistan. According to the National Statistics and Information Authority (NSIA), there are 2,846 private schools in Afghanistan, educating 930,663 students with the assistance of 42,506 teachers (NSIA, 2023).

This research addresses job satisfaction by using a comprehensive approach to the factors that influence the level of satisfaction. Thus, specialized literature advances the level of knowledge with complex results related to jobs.

2. Literature Review

In the literature, several theories have been developed to explain job satisfaction. One such theory, which includes variables similar to those examined in the present study, is Frederick Herzberg's dual-structure theory. Developed in the late 1950s and early 1960s, this theory is also known as the two-factor theory. Herzberg's theory posits a distinction between job satisfaction and the concepts of satisfaction and dissatisfaction. According to this theory, an

employee can experience both satisfaction and dissatisfaction simultaneously, leading to the perception of two distinct dimensions or factors. The first dimension is the "motivation" factor, which includes elements that contribute to employee satisfaction and motivation. These factors, such as recognition and achievement, ensure that employees remain satisfied and motivated in their tasks. The absence of these factors may result in dissatisfaction; however, employees might still find satisfaction in other aspects of their job. The second dimension is the "hygiene" factor, which relates to elements that typically lead to feelings of dissatisfaction and a lack of motivation. Herzberg's study revealed that inadequacies in factors like pay/salary, job security, working conditions, and supervision could cause employees to feel dissatisfied and unmotivated. Nonetheless, other factors might still contribute to job satisfaction even in the presence of such inadequacies. (Griffin & Moorhead, 2013)

Based on the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (Weiss, Dawis, & England, 1967) and comprehensive literature review, several crucial factors influence job satisfaction. The following sections discuss these factors in detail.

1.1. Job Security

The findings of recent research on the retention intention and job satisfaction of teachers demonstrate that extraversion and social support positively affect retention intentions and job satisfaction of employees. Consequently, the study recommends that school administrators should endeavor to support their teachers in order to enhance retention (Richter, Lucksnat, Redding, & Richter, 2022).

According to research by (Artz & Kaya, 2014) job security significantly enhances job satisfaction, particularly during periods of economic contraction. The authors further argued that job security does not hold the same value for employees with higher levels of education in terms of job satisfaction when compared to employees with lower levels of education.

The teachers of private schools in Afghanistan are more satisfied in comparison to the public schools. However, with respect to job security, the teachers in public schools are more satisfied (Noori, 2023).

1.2. Working Conditions

A relevant study reveals a positive relationship between "job characteristics," "work environment," and the "social aspect of the job" with "organizational commitment" (Dalkrani

& Dimitriadis, 2018). The results of another study indicate that involving employees in decision-making processes enhances job satisfaction and subsequently improves their performance (Yuspahrudin, et al., 2020).

Another study also reveals a linear relationship between job satisfaction and employee performance in Nigeria (Ndulue & Ekechukwu, 2016). However, the study indicates that employees are mostly dissatisfied with their working conditions of the company. Consequently, the researchers recommend that the organization's management provide appropriate working conditions to foster employee comfort and improve workplace morale.

1.3. *Advancement*

A study is conducted on teachers' well-being and job satisfaction in Germany (Dreer, 2024). The sample of the study consisted of 551 German school teachers. The results show that achievement, positive emotions, engagement, relationships, and meaning have significant relationships with job satisfaction.

Another recent study underlines the significance of career advancement for employees (Fütterer, Waveren, Hübner, Fischer, & Sälzer, 2023). The study's findings suggest that additional certifications and opportunities for professional growth are instrumental in enhancing job satisfaction. Specifically, the research concludes that career advancement plays an essential role in influencing the job satisfaction of educators.

Another study analyzed the determinants of job satisfaction with regard to professional advancement (Ankudinov, Lebedev, & Sachenkov, 2015). The study confirms a strong influence of employee function and financial incentives on satisfaction with professional advancement.

1.4. *Coworker Relationship*

A comparative study has been conducted to examine the levels of job satisfaction among lecturers in higher education institutions in Pakistan (Hameed, Ahmad-Baig, & Cacheiro-Gonzalez, 2018). This study reveals statistically significant differences in the degree of agreement and opinions between lecturers from private and public universities. The results indicate a general dissatisfaction among lecturers regarding salary, promotion opportunities, benefits, relationships with coworkers, nature of work, and communication. Additionally, a

study on “The Quality of the Social Environment at Work and Job Satisfaction” reveals that the intensity of association between job satisfaction and quality of relationship with supervisor is greater compare to coworkers (Repetti & Cosmas, 1991).

1.5. Recognition

A study focused on Ford Motor Private Ltd. has established a linear relationship between employee empowerment and job satisfaction, suggesting that employees require a sense of motivation for improved performance (Kumari & Hemalatha, 2018). The findings indicate that empowering employees significantly influences their satisfaction and commitment. This empowerment can be facilitated through various means, including training, communication, recognition, and valuing their feedback and suggestions. Another study concludes that the reward system plays a significant role and has a strong positive linear relationship with job satisfaction and employee performance (Aktar, Sachu, & Uddin, 2013). However, the impact of these rewards varies according to age, gender, and educational level.

1.6. Achievement

A recent study on job satisfaction demonstrates that, as satisfaction in specific areas of work life increases, so does the overall level of satisfaction in critical aspects of work, such as achievement and a sense of fairness (Tomaszewska, Kowalczyk, Majchrowicz, Kłos, & Kalita, 2024).

Further research undertaken by (Salleh, Musadik, & Nor, 2023) examines the impact of achievement, recognition, leadership, and Islamic work ethics on job satisfaction among lecturers at Ungku Omar Polytechnic. The findings of the study indicate a positive correlation between achievement and job satisfaction among the lecturers within the studied population. Another study conducted by (Dunnette, Campbel, & Hakel, 1967) states that achievement can result in both job satisfaction and dissatisfaction.

1.7. Compensation

A study conducted by (Sahibzada, Tolossa, & Pandya, 2022) indicates that the higher amount of payment leads to higher level of job satisfaction among the teaching staff at Paktia University in Afghanistan. A similar study conducted by (Lin & Zhao, 2024) claims that

financial benefits and work-family life balance are strong factors for determining job satisfaction. Additionally, authors emphasize the cultural significance of financial stability and family harmony in Taiwanese society.

Another study states that employee performance can be optimal if the employee is satisfied with their compensation package, job security, and reward system (Awan & Asghar, 2014). Furthermore, there is a significant relationship between financial benefits and other types of rewards with the employee's level of satisfaction (Latif, et al., 2013). Employees in higher management positions are more satisfied with intrinsic rewards, while those in lower-level positions are more satisfied with extrinsic rewards. As a result, higher level of employee satisfaction leads to reduced absenteeism, lower turnover rates, increased productivity, and enhanced performance.

Based on the above literature review, we aim to identify the determinants of job satisfaction among private school teachers in Afghanistan. Furthermore, we would like to answer the following research question:

What are the significant determinants of job satisfaction among the school teachers in Afghanistan?

3. Research Methodology

The objective of the study is to identify the determinants of job satisfaction in private schools in Afghanistan. The target population for this study comprises all private school instructors in Kabul City, the capital of Afghanistan. According to estimates by the NSIA, there are 1,427 private schools and 22,037 private school instructors in Kabul (NSIA, 2023).

The sample size was calculated using an online sample size calculator (Raosoft) with a 6.5% margin of error and a 95% confidence interval. Typically, the margin of error is chosen to be between five and ten percent. Based on these parameters, the sample size was determined to be 224 respondents. Consequently, questionnaires were distributed to respondents in line with the calculated sample size. However, the total number of completed and returned questionnaires amounted to 206. After excluding unengaged responses, the final number of valid respondents was 172. The collected data were thoroughly examined to ensure the reliability and validity of the measurements.

The questionnaire utilized in this study comprises 35 questions and seven variables, organized into two main sections. The first section captures demographic information,

including gender, age, education, and job experience. The second section contains items related to job satisfaction. The questions pertaining to the variables were selected from the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (Weiss, Dawis, & England, 1967).

A pilot test was conducted, and seven variables were chosen based on their contextual relevance and the results of the reliability test. These variables include compensation, working conditions, advancement, coworker relationships, recognition, security, and achievement. Specifically:

Compensation: refers to the pay and the amount of work done.

Working Conditions: denote the working environment of the employees.

Advancement: involves the opportunities for career progression available to the employees.

Coworker Relationships: describe how well employees get along with their coworkers.

Recognition: pertains to the praise received by employees for their job performance.

Security: indicates the stability of employment.

Achievement: is the sense of accomplishment that employees derive from their job.

Each variable comprises five questions, measured using a Likert Scale, where ratings are 5 for "very satisfied," 4 for "satisfied," 3 for "neither satisfied nor dissatisfied," 2 for "dissatisfied," and 1 for "very dissatisfied".

To analyze the data, the researchers employed Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), utilizing Stata and SPSS statistical software. The conceptual model suggested by the authors is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Conceptual Model

Source: Own creation

Job satisfaction is considered a latent variable in this study. Nevertheless, the seven variables (compensation, working conditions, advancement, coworker relationships, recognition, security, and achievement) are observed, with each variable being measured through five items. The specific items used in this research are detailed in Table 2. All necessary tests have been conducted to ensure the reliability and validity of the scales utilized in this study.

4. Findings

Table 1 provides a comprehensive overview of the personal details and demographic information of the sample population. The majority of the respondents are female, amounting to 133 participants. Regarding professional experience, a significant portion of participants, 47 individuals, have two years of experience, followed by 39 individuals with six or more years of experience. In terms of educational attainment, 136 respondents hold a bachelor's degree, while 7 respondents possess a master's degree.

Table 1: Personal Details of Respondents

	Frequency	Percent
Gender		
Female	133	64.6
Male	73	35.4
Total	206	100
Experience		
1 and less than a year	39	19
2	47	22.8
3	41	19.9
4	22	10.7
5	18	8.7
6 years and above	39	18.9
Total	206	100
Education		
Bachelor	136	66.0
Baccalaureate	63	30.6
Master	7	3.4
Total	206	100

Age		
[17-30]	187	90.8
[31-40]	17	8.2
[41-50]	2	1.0
Total	206	100

Source: Own computation (SPSS results)

To ensure the reliability of the items, Cronbach's alpha values were calculated in Table 2. The generally accepted threshold for Cronbach's alpha is 0.7 and above (Taber, 2017). The results of this study indicate a higher average Cronbach's alpha value of 0.8, which exceeds the commonly accepted value, thus confirming the reliability of the scales used.

Table 2: Reliability Test

No	Variable	Selected Questions From MSQ					Cronbach's Alpha
1	Security (JS)	11	31	51	71	91	0.8
2	Working conditions (WC)	13	33	53	73	93	0.8
3	Advancement (Ad)	14	34	54	74	94	0.9
4	Coworker (CW)	16	36	56	76	96	0.7
5	Recognition (R)	18	38	58	78	98	0.9
6	Achievement (A)	19	39	59	79	99	0.7
7	Compensation (C)	12	32	52	72	92	0.9
Average							0.8

Source: Own computation (SPSS results)

Furthermore, in Table 3 the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's tests were conducted to assess the adequacy of the sample size and the suitability of the scales used in this study. The KMO value obtained is 0.95, which exceeds the commonly accepted threshold of 0.7 (Lloret, Ferreres, Hernández, & Tomás, 2017), indicating that the sample size is adequate. Additionally, the P-value for Bartlett's test is smaller than 0.01, demonstrating that the test is statistically significant. These results affirm the appropriateness of the sample and the scales for the data analysis.

Table 3: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.928
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	2497.488
	df	300
	Sig.	.000

Source: Own computation (SPSS results)

Figure 2 depicts the factor loadings of the data. As illustrated in Figure 2, all the factor loadings are well above 0.6, with the exception of compensation, which has a value of 0.6. Despite this, the components are still considered to be well-related to job satisfaction.

To achieve a better model fit, we considered the covariance of the errors, specifically e2, e7, and e4. This covariance was identified using post-estimation tests.

Figure 2: Calculated CFA

Source: Own creation

The results are further detailed in Table 4, which presents the measurements along with their respective coefficients and p-values. From Table 4, it can be concluded that all the measures introduced in the research significantly contribute to job satisfaction among teachers in the surveyed schools, as evidenced by p-values in the last column being less than the threshold of acceptance (0.05). Therefore, the measures of job satisfaction employed are statistically significant.

Additionally, the results in Table 4 indicate that achievement has the highest influence on job satisfaction, possessing the greatest coefficient of 0.869, followed by coworker relationships. In contrast, compensation exhibits the lowest coefficient of 0.589.

Table 4: CFA Results

Structural equation model	Number of obs	=	172
Estimation method	= ml		
Log likelihood	= -1408.6751		
		OIM	
	Standardized		Coef. Std. Err. z P> z
Measurement			
Achievement <-			
JobSatisfaction		.8690024	.025389 34.23 0.000
_cons		3.763898	.2167876 17.36 0.000
Advancement <-			
JobSatisfaction		.6999056	.043998 15.91 0.000
_cons		2.959346	.1768402 16.73 0.000
WorkingCondition <-			
JobSatisfaction		.8187083	.03101 26.40 0.000
_cons		3.755595	.2163687 17.36 0.000
Compensation <-			
JobSatisfaction		.5890215	.0549825 10.71 0.000
_cons		2.970682	.1773919 16.75 0.000
Coworker <-			
JobSatisfaction		.7904667	.0335961 23.53 0.000
_cons		3.848695	.2210733 17.41 0.000
Recognition <-			
JobSatisfaction		.6849611	.0450457 15.21 0.000
_cons		3.328016	.1949634 17.07 0.000
JobSecurity <-			
JobSatisfaction		.7894552	.0339675 23.24 0.000
_cons		3.355022	.1963043 17.09 0.000
var(e.Achievement)		.2448349	.0441262

var(e.Advancement)	.5101321	.0615889		
var(e.WorkingCondition)	.3297168	.0507763		
var(e.Compensation)	.6530537	.0647717		
var(e.Coworker)	.3751625	.0531132		
var(e.Recognition)	.5308283	.0617091		
var(e.JobSecurity)	.3767605	.0536317		
var(JobSatisfaction)	1	.		
cov(e.Advancement,e.Compensation)	.2907519	.0755685	3.85	0.000
cov(e.Advancement,e.JobSecurity)	.3659057	.0751262	4.87	0.000
cov(e.Compensation,e.JobSecurity)	.2043326	.0827366	2.47	0.014
LR test of model vs. saturated: chi2(11)=14.62, Prob > chi2 =0.2003				

Source: Own computation (Stata results)

Ensuring the model fit of the data is crucial. The results of several statistical tests conducted using Stata are presented in Table 5. Although the chi-square test is significant, which ideally should be insignificant for the model to be considered a good fit, additional tests were conducted to confirm the model fit.

The root mean squared error of approximation (RMSEA) value is 0.044, which is within the acceptable range below 0.05 (Hu & Bentler, 1999). The pclose (p of close fit) value is 0.518, exceeding the acceptable threshold of more than 0.05. Additionally, the comparative fit index (CFI) and Tucker-Lewis index (TLI) values are 0.995 and 0.99, respectively, both of which surpass the minimum acceptable value of 0.95 (Hu & Bentler, 1999).

Considering all the values mentioned above, the model used for confirmatory factor analysis is deemed to be a good fit.

Table 5: Over All Goodness of Fit

Fit statistic	Value	Description
Likelihood ratio		
chi2_ms(11)	14.625	model vs. saturated
p > chi2	0.200	
chi2_bs(21)	715.576	baseline vs. saturated
p > chi2	0.000	
Population error		

RMSEA		0.044	Root mean squared error of approximation
90% CI, lower bound		0.000	
upper bound		0.097	
pclose		0.518	Probability RMSEA <= 0.05
Information criteria			
AIC		2865.350	Akaike's information criterion
BIC		2940.890	Bayesian information criterion
Baseline comparison			
CFI		0.995	Comparative fit index
TLI		0.990	Tucker-Lewis index
Size of residuals			
SRMR		0.026	Standardized root mean squared residual
CD		0.907	Coefficient of determination

Source: Own computation (Stata results)

5. Discussions

The experience of private schooling in Afghanistan is relatively recent. A few private high schools were established in 2004, following the collapse of the first Taliban regime and the formation of the new government led by former President Hamid Karzai. According to the National Statistics and Information Authority (NSIA, 2023), schools in Afghanistan accommodate approximately 9.25 million students, of whom 40.45% are girls. Additionally, private schools provide significant employment opportunities for teachers. Thus, understanding the factors that contribute to teacher satisfaction in these institutions is essential.

The findings of this research indicate that compensation, working conditions, advancement, coworker relationships, recognition, security, and achievement are key determinants of job satisfaction for teachers in private schools. Notably, achievement has the highest coefficient, making it the most significant factor influencing job satisfaction.

Our study concludes that working conditions are a determinant of job satisfaction, confirming findings from (Ndulue & Ekechukwu, 2016). Additionally, we found that advancement is a determinant of job satisfaction, which is supported by similar findings in another research, such as (Fütterer, Waveren, Hübner, Fischer, & Sälzer, 2023). Coworker relationships were also identified as a determinant of job satisfaction, a conclusion supported by (Hameed, Ahmad-Baig, & Cacheiro-Gonzalez, 2018).

Recognition is a significant factor for job satisfaction, a result consistent with the literature, including (Kumari & Hemalatha, 2018). Moreover, achievement is another crucial factor for employee satisfaction among school teachers, a conclusion supported by (Dunnette, Campbel, & Hakel, 1967) as well as (Salleh, Musadik, & Nor, 2023). Finally, compensation is a vital factor for job satisfaction among teachers, as claimed by similar studies conducted by (Awan & Asghar, 2014) and (Latif, et al., 2013).

The results of similar research in the banking sector corroborate our findings, demonstrating a positive association between job satisfaction and factors such as awards, remuneration, job security, promotion opportunities, and good relations with colleagues (Bhardwaj, Mishra, & Jain, 2021). Furthermore, research on the dimensions of academicians' job satisfaction conducted at public research universities in Klang Valley, Malaysia, supports the determinants identified in the present study. The research in Malaysia indicated that most academicians reported a high level of satisfaction with their pay (compensation), coworker relationships, promotion, supervision, and overall work experience (Mehrad, 2021).

6. Conclusion

As teachers are a substantial asset for private schools, understanding the factors influencing their job satisfaction is crucial. In this research, seven determinants of job satisfaction have been identified. These determinants exhibit varying degrees of influence on job satisfaction. Among them, achievement which is defined as the sense of accomplishment employees derive from their work, emerges as the most valuable determinant of job satisfaction. Conversely, while compensation is also considered a determinant of job satisfaction, it has a comparatively lesser influence.

The findings of this study have both theoretical and practical implications. Theoretically, our findings, supported by statistical tests, contribute to the existing body of knowledge on job satisfaction determinants. Practically, school managers and other relevant stakeholders can utilize the findings of this study to enhance employee satisfaction. By understanding and addressing the concrete factors identified in this research, decision-makers can implement strategies that align with these determinants, thereby achieving their business objectives and fostering a more satisfied and productive workforce.

In the present research, several minor challenges or limitations were encountered. First, there was a lack of cooperation from some respondents. Second, the research was limited to

Kabul City. For future studies, it is recommended to expand the scope to include other provinces, particularly larger ones such as Herat, Balkh, Qandahar, and Nangrahar.

References

- Aktar, S., Sachu, M., & Uddin, M. (2013). The impact of rewards on job satisfaction and employees' performance in Bangladesh: A comparative analysis between pharmaceutical and insurance Industries. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*, 2(8), S. 1-8.
- Dalkrani, M., & Dimitriadis, E. (2018). The Effect of Job Satisfaction on Employee Commitment. *International Journal of Business and Economic Sciences Applied Research*, 11(3), 16-23.
- Ankudinov, A. B., Lebedev, O. V., & Sachenkov, A. A. (2015). Empirical Analysis of Job Satisfaction Determinants in Russia. *Asian Social Science*, 11(9), S. 117-125.
- Artz, B., & Kaya, I. (2014). The impact of job security on jobsatisfaction in economiccontractions versus expansions. *Applied Economics*, 46(24), S. 2873–2890.
- Ashraf, M., Ahmad, N., Shaikh, O. A., Bhatti, S. R., & Soomro, A. H. (2013). The determinants of job satisfaction in public service organization. *European scientific journal*, 9(35), 362-377.
- Awan, A. G., & Asghar, I. (2014). Impact of employee job satisfaction on their performance a case study of banking sector in muzaffargarh district, pakistan. *Global Journal of Human Resource Management*, 2(4), 71-94.
- Bhardwaj, A., Mishra, S., & Jain, T. K. (2021). An analysis to understanding the job satisfaction of employees in banking industry. *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 37(2), 170-174.
- Breaugh, J. (1981). Predicting absenteeism from prior absenteeism and work attitudes. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 66(5), S. 555-560.
- Chen, P., & Spector, P. (1992). Relationship of work stressors with aggression, withdrawal, theft and substance use: An exploratory study. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 65, S. 177-184.
- Dormann, C., & Zapf, D. (2001). Job satisfaction: a meta-analysis of stabilities. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 22(5), S. 483-504.
- Dreer, B. (2024). Teachers' well-being and job satisfaction: the important role of positive emotions in the workplace. *Educational Studies*, 50(1), S. 61-77.
- Dunnette, M., Campbel, J., & Hakel, M. (1967). Factors Contributing to Job Satisfaction and Job Dissatisfaction in Six Occupational Groups. *Organizational behaviour and human performance*, 2, S. 143-174.
- Farkas, A., & Tetrick, L. (1989). A three-wave longitudinal analysis of the causal ordering of satisfaction and commitment on turnover decisions. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 74(6), S. 855–868.
- Fütterer, T., Waveren, L., Hübner, N., Fischer, C., & Sälzer, C. (January 2023). I can't get no (job) satisfaction? Differences in teachers' job satisfaction from a career pathways perspective. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 121, S. 103942. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2022.103942>
- Gottfredson, G., & Holland, J. (1990). A longitudinal test of the influence of congruence: Job satisfaction, competency utilization, and counterproductive behavior. *Journal of Counseling Psychology*, 37(4), S. 389–398.
- Griffin, R. W., & Moorhead, G. (2013). *Organizational Behavior: Managing People and Organizations* (11th Ausg.). Cengage Learning.
- Hackman, J., & Oldham, G. (1980). *Work Redesign*. Addison-Wesley: Reading, Mass.

- Hameed, F., Ahmad-Baig, I., & Cacheiro-Gonzalez, M. L. (2018). Job Satisfaction of Teachers from Public and Private sector Universities In Lahore Pakistan: A Comparative Study. *Economics & Sociology, 11*(4), S. 230-245.
- Hu, L.-t., & Bentler, P. M. (1999). Cutoff criteria for fit indexes in covariance structure analysis: Conventional criteria versus new alternatives. *Structural Equation Modeling: A Multidisciplinary Journal, 6*(1), S. 1-55.
- Keller, R. T. (1983). Predicting absenteeism from prior absenteeism, attitudinal factors, and nonattitudinal factors. *Journal of Applied Psychology, 68*(3), S. 536-540.
- Kumari, P., & Hemalatha, A. (2018). A Study on Impact of Employee Empowerment on Job Satisfaction with Reference to Ford Motor Private Ltd, Perungudi. *Eurasian Journal of Analytical Chemistry, 13*, S. 61-67.
- Latif, M., Ahmad, M., Qasim, M., Mushtaq, M., Ferdoos, A., & Naeem, H. (2013). Impact of employee's job satisfaction on organizational performance. *European Journal of Business and Management, 5*(5), 166-171.
- Lin, C., & Zhao, J. (2024). Testing the determinants of job satisfaction among police administrative officers in Taiwan. *Policing: An International Journal*. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1108/PIJPSM-11-2023-0145>
- Lloret, S., Ferreres, A., Hernández, A., & Tomás, I. (2017). The exploratory factor analysis of items: guided analysis based on empirical data and software. *Anales de psicología, 33*(2), S. 417-432.
- Locke, E. (1969). What is Job Satisfaction? *Organizational Behavior and Human Performance, 4*, S. 309-336.
- Mehrad, A. (2021). Pay, Promotion, Work, Supervision, and Coworker as Dimensions of Academicians Job Satisfaction at Public Research Universities in Klang Valley, Malaysia. *Journal of Social Science Research, 17*, 55-60.
- Ndulue, T. I., & Ekechukwu, H. C. (July 2016). Impact of Job Satisfaction on Employees Performance: A Study of Nigerian Breweries PLC Kaduna State Branch, Nigeria. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review (AJBMR), 33*(3820), 1-11.
- Noori, A. Q. (2023). Job satisfaction variance among public and private school teachers: A case study. *Cogent Education, 10*(1), S. 1-18.
- NSIA. (2023). *Afghanistan Statistical yearbook*. Abgerufen am 2024 von National Statistics and Information Authority.
- Repetti, R. L., & Cosmas, K. A. (1991). The Quality of the Social Environment at Work and Job Satisfaction. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology, 21*(10), S. 791-874.
- Richter, E., Lucksnat, C., Redding, C., & Richter, D. (2022). Retention intention and job satisfaction of alternatively certified teachers in their first year of teaching. *Teaching and Teacher Education, 114*, S. 1-11.
- Rusbult, C., & Farrel, D. (1983). A longitudinal test of the investment model: The impact on job satisfaction, job commitment, and turnover of variations in rewards, costs, alternatives, and investments. *Journal of Applied Psychology, 68*(3), S. 429-438.
- Sahibzada, A., Tolossa, D. N., & Pandya, H. B. (2022). The Relationship Between Job Satisfaction and the Performance of Employees at Paktia University, Afghanistan. *GAP iINTERDISCIPLINARITIES A Global Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies, 6*(4), S. 7-10.
- Salleh, H., Musadik, S., & Nor, M. (2023). The influence of achievement, recognition, leadership and islamic work ethics towards job satisfaction among lecturers in Ungku Omar Ploythechnic. *Azka Interantional Journal of Zakat and Social Finance, 4*(3), S. 67-86.
- Taber, K. S. (2017). The Use of Cronbach's Alpha When Developing and Reporting Research Instruments in Science Education. *48*, S. 1273–1296.

- Tharenou, P. (1993). A test of reciprocal causality for absenteeism. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 14(3), S. 269-287.
- Tomaszewska, K., Kowalczyk, K., Majchrowicz, B., Kłos, A., & Kalita, K. (2024). Areas of professional life and job satisfaction of nurses. *Frontier Public Health*, 12.
- Vulley, D. K. (2021). Factors Influencing Teacher Job Satisfaction and Commitment at Senior High Schools in the Greater Accra Region, Ghana. *European Journal of Education Studies*, 8(3), S. 46-65.
- Weiss, D. J., Dawis, R. V., & England, G. W. (1967). Manual for the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire. *Minnesota Studies in Vocational Rehabilitation*.
- Yuspahrudin, A., Eliyana, A., Buchdadi, A. D., Hamidah, Sariwulan, T., & Muhaziroh, K. (2020). The Effect of Employee Involvement on Job Satisfaction. *Systematic Reviews in Pharmacy*, 11(7), S. 490-498.